

APPLICATION OF AGENT-BASED MODELING IN DECISION- MAKING MIGRATION POLICY

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the analysis of existing experience in the application of agent-based approach by modeling migration processes carried out for ongoing development of complex agent-based models to simulate processes in the field of migration policy. Analysis showed that despite the advantages demonstrated by the agent-based approach compared with traditional methods of demographic research simulation reveals various difficulties in terms of simulating migration processes that nevertheless do not underestimate advantages of agent and other existing modeling approaches. Hybrid population-based agent modeling is a new emerging field of study that showed advantages by implementing this approach. The explosive population growth around the world over the past few decades has had an enormous impact on the level of natural resources, the state of the environment and the structure of society in many countries. The study of demographic and migratory trends and the dynamics of changes in the population structure plays a key role in the formation of domestic as well as global policies to achieve sustainable social and environmental development.

Keywords: *agent-based modeling, EU economy, migration, migration policy*

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, demography is an empirical discipline in the social sciences, aimed at the study of long-term change processes at the population level (Burch, 2018). Nevertheless, in recent years, a growing level of criticism has been observed in this area in relation to the unsatisfactory level of theoretical substantiation and explanation of various demographic phenomena (Hobcraft, 2007). Modern demographic research faces three important issues (Silverman, 2013). Firstly, for the correct description of the demographic phenomena and the proper definition of political objectives, demographic analysis should be carried out at different levels of aggregation: from individuals, households and regions to society (Courgeau, 2016). Attempts to solve this problem have recently been undertaken by interlinking a multi-level statistical analysis of time series with micromodelling (Klabunde, 2015). However, the use of aggregation does not guarantee a high accuracy of the forecast, and an increase in the dimensionality in models reduces the quality of forecasting due to the increased sensitivity to the amount of source data, as well as their deficit. The second problem consists in conjunction with other statistical meaningful information for the identification of new trends in the context of demographic processes. Finally, the third task is to determine the level of detail of the developed demographic models, as well as the degree of use of empirical data. From the standpoint of potential in solving the above-mentioned problems, an agent-based modeling (hereinafter - ABM) differs substantially from statistical methods, because this approach allows considering the phenomena for which there is no clear analytical representation (Makarov, 2016). In this regard, the ABM is an effective tool for analyzing and explaining non-linear or complex

interactions, such as the social nature of behavior, including various difficult to formalize elements (for example, social context, networks of interpersonal relationships, etc.). This article is devoted to the analysis of the existing experience of using an agent-based approach to the modeling of migration processes, carried out with the aim of further developing a set of agent-based models that simulate the processes in the field of migration policy.

2. RETURN MIGRATION MODEL

With the help of SESSL (Ewald, 2014) and ML3 (Warnke, 2015) technologies, a model simulating the process of return migration was developed in (Reinhardt, 2018). Migrants have several characteristics that affect their financial condition, as well as the desire to return to their homeland. The intensity of migration flows based on the statistics of the Office of National Statistics, UK. The age of migrants is of great importance during the simulation, since after reaching the retirement age, agents are excluded from the model. Simulated migrants are also endowed with a randomly defined "skill level" that affects their potential income level. In addition, the model has a network character, since each migrant has his own social network of connections. When the model is initialized, the intensity of the emergence of migrants depends on the difference between the current average earnings and the target earnings of agents (Harris, 1970). In addition, the total income of agents is influenced by social capital associated with the scale of the migrant network (Portes 1998), access to loans and mortgages, etc. During the simulation, migrant agents adhere to one of two strategies: permanent relocation to another country, or accumulation of capital enough for comfortable living at home (Constant, 2002). A series of multiple experiments showed that the SESSL language allowed us to implement and integrate a new experimental design method for demographic models. Combining regression metamodels and a Gaussian process emulator with the methods supported by SESSL showed that the nature of the distribution of migrant strategies and the nature of their network connections are crucial in the demographic development process.

3. NETWORK MODEL OF MIGRATION ADAPTATION

Model (Simon, 2019) is implemented in a multi-agent, programmable simulation environment Netlogo. At initialization pattern generated population of agents 272, which is distributed over the cells in the space. As the source data was used the database "Mexican Migration Project"¹, as well as data from alternative sources. Due to the inability to establish the nature of network connections of the Mexican communities, the researchers chose the network topology of the "close world", which has a high level of clustering, as well as a low distance between nodes (Watts, 1998). At the start of the simulation, agents make decisions about emigration depending on their current location and salary amount. In the course of the simulation, a comparison is made of indicators of wage levels in the "home" and "foreign" regions, which influence the decision-making of agents on emigration. In addition, immigrants engaged in labor activities can make remittances to their relatives in order to compensate for the costs of emigration. Agents located in the "home" region during emulation make decisions about emigration, and the change in the number of migrants influences their actual wages. However, as emigrants send information and monetary resources to their relatives, this also affects the expected incomes of non-migrants, and, consequently, their usefulness in terms of labor migration, as well as the amount of accumulated resources. The simulation results showed that, regardless of political restrictions, agents move most intensively to areas with a high concentration of emigrants ("Diasporas") on their territory. This tendency weakens only in the case of extremely unfavorable conditions for migration. Areas with no "Diasporas" absent in the territory become dominant from the point of view of emigration only in the event of a significant weakening of the policy of restraining migration flows.

¹ mmp.opr.princeton.edu

According to the theory of social networks, the simulation results showed a tendency of migrant agents to move to areas with the presence of “Diasporas” even when political conditions are very favorable for moving to an alternative destination. However, in the event of a return migration, migration flows may vary depending on different political conditions. In this case, a liberal “alternative direction” may attract more migrants than a restrictive “traditional direction”. The simulation results also showed that the process of moving agents in space could become unstable in the case when both “directions” have similar political conditions. In that case, the model shows a decrease in the size of the diaspora as agents return and re-migrate, which, in turn, leads to the formation of more uniform migration flows between regions.

4. HYBRID POPULATION AGENT-BASED MODELING

The article discusses the advantages of applying a hybrid approach to modeling processes using micro- and agent-based modeling. Taking advantage of the two tools gives researchers an opportunity to study such complex population issues as the gender gap, welfare gap, migration, the relationship between the labor market and macroeconomic policies, epidemic diseases, etc. The construction of such models can be divided into 4 main stages: the collection of various data on the target population (gender and age structure, geographical distribution, etc.) (Moeckel, 2003); calculating missing data; building a behavioral model of agents; conducting scenario modeling and analysis. Hybrid population-based agent modeling is a new emerging field of study, but currently there are already advantages in implementing this approach. First, the agent-based approach allows for a more in-depth and detailed study of decision-making mechanisms. On the other hand, micromodelling has advantages in the context of collecting the data obtained in the course of modeling, with a view to their further presentation, evaluation and validation under empirical conditions. Thus, hybrid population simulation, which combines agent-based technologies with basic synthetic population data, can lay a solid foundation for social modeling.

5. CONCLUSION

An analysis of the existing experience of using an agent-based approach in the field of migration policy showed that, despite the advantages demonstrated by the agent-based approach compared with traditional methods of demographic research, modeling reveals various difficulties from the position of imitating migration processes (Morand, 2010). Firstly, modeling in the social sciences usually concentrates on very specific aspects of social behavior (Bahtizin, 2018). For example, in order to apply standard statistical analysis, which implies a “static” random connection between variables, it seems necessary to distinguish causal factors in social actions and social properties (so-called structuring factors). Algorithms of imitation of a particular social behavior should be initially simplified as much as possible in order to be able to add various structuring factors from the wider social environment. Current social theories, in a sense, do not represent adequate prerequisites for designing agent-oriented models. Thus, the set of statistical laws that sociologists use to predict the behavior of groups of the population turns out to be inapplicable in modeling individual agent-based behavior. Therefore, the agent modeling process cannot rely on existing theories, since they are either overly abstracted or empirically unrealistic. Because social interactions are always special in terms of context (including the time and place of their occurrence), consideration of this aspect is an integral part in the behavior of agents and has a high impact on their decisions. However, taking into account such contexts could with high popularity lead to significant non-linearity and clustering of information transfer flows between agents, which will require considerable complication of behavioral algorithms in the model and can be considered as contradicting the idea of initially having lightweight models. Modeling an agent with a complex nature of social interaction is also another extremely difficult task, in the context of providing agents with the ability to store

and use large amounts of statistical information. Finally, in many multi-agent systems, due attention is not paid to the data needed to calibrate the designed models. Currently, questionnaires are the dominant measure for gathering information about how people make decisions. However, the analysis of the principles of decision-making by people requires the development of new technologies to collect the necessary data. However, the above difficulties do not diminish the advantages of agent and other existing approaches to modeling. On the contrary, both agent-based models and their traditional statistical and mathematical analogs have both advantages and disadvantages in the context of a detailed presentation of the social behavior of the subjects studied.

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